

SOCIAL SCIENCES

COMMUNICATION AS A LINGUISTIC PROBLEM

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Abstract

Communication, as a field of scientific knowledge, has a long history, evidenced by the fact that the term has several definitions. This term is used in sociology, political science, psychology, linguistics, and so forth, which confirms that various professionals encounter communication problems.

Communication is a social process. It performs a connecting function in society. Communication does not occur only in human social systems; certain types of communication are characteristic of animals and birds (bird songs, the language of bees, etc.). We also use the concept of "communication" when referring to technical means and mechanisms created by humans (transport, telegraph and telephone signals, computer systems, etc.).

Beyond pure content, the communication process also expresses the mutual relationship between communication partners and, based on this, how the receiver should understand the sender's message. The relational aspect of communication shows what emotional attitude communication partners have toward each other. It determines the content aspect, since the mutual relationship between communication partners directs their mutual understanding. We have optimal communication when harmony prevails between the content and relational aspects, or when disagreement at the content level is not followed by complications at the relational level. The task of the content aspect is to deliver information. The relational aspect reveals how the receiver understood the relationship.

Keywords: communication process, sender, message, content aspect, relational aspect.

Introduction: The problems of researching communication processes belong to the list of humanity's pressing issues. "In humanity's history, the leading position of communication emphatically explains why so many different fields of knowledge attempt to study communication processes, such as: anthropology, art, education, ethnology, history, journalism, law, linguistics, philosophy, political science, psychology, and sociology," wrote Erik Barnouw, a renowned theorist of mass communication. In the broad sense, communication is the transmission of messages, the exchange of thoughts and information—that is, interaction. During communication, through signs, some content is transmitted from one mind (whether collective or individual) to another. Communication is the sharing of information, ideas, emotions, news, and so forth through symbols (whether words, images, graphics, or something else). Communication is a process that connects separate parts of the world with each other. During communication, what was previously the monopoly of one or a few becomes universally known.

Traditionally, communication between people is understood as the exchange of information through a unified system of symbols in general, and specifically through linguistic signs. The formation of this field of knowledge begins from ancient times, though interest in the problem of communication became particularly acute in the 20th century. It transcended the boundaries of linguistics and psychology; moreover, even psycholinguistics and sociolinguistics. The problem of

modeling interaction—whether machine to machine, human to human, or human to machine—became the subject of consideration in cybernetics as the science of management and the theory of artificial intelligence. The development of information and communication means led us to mass communication media, while the perfection of production relations placed the issue in the sphere of communication management. Thus, today the study of communication processes already represents one of humanity's most pressing and global issues.

Communication between people is carried out through verbal and non-verbal means. Non-verbal includes, for example, visual means of communication: cinema, painting, and so forth. The renowned culturologist Umberto Eco understands communication more broadly: "Culture is largely communication." More widespread is the view according to which everything that surrounds a person, including culture, constitutes a communicative environment. It is precisely verbal (oral and written) communication that is the primary, universal form of interaction, encoding, and information transmission for humans. The classic formula of communication is considered to be the definition of American researcher Harold Lasswell: who says what to whom, through what channel, with what effect.

Review and Discussion: Every communication has content and relational aspects, with the latter determining the former. The participant in communication transmits certain content, a certain

message. Beyond pure content, the communication process also expresses the mutual relationship between communication partners and, based on this, how the receiver should understand the sender's message. Often the same content means one thing to a stranger and something else to a friend. The relational aspect of communication shows what emotional attitude communication partners have toward each other. It determines the content aspect, since the mutual relationship between communication partners directs their mutual understanding. We have optimal communication when harmony prevails between the content and relational aspects, or when disagreement at the content level is not followed by complications at the relational level. The task of the content aspect is to deliver information. The relational aspect reveals how the receiver understood the relationship. Regarding communication in general, it can be said that purely informational communication does not exist. Every utterance also contains a relational aspect.

The process of interaction is mutual influence, and the result of interaction is the emotion that we leave on each other. Consider that a person who cannot leave a certain type of emotion during interaction has spoken in vain.

As a rule, people primarily voice their desires. That is, our communication is not typically results-oriented. I say what I want. But why should you do what I want? Communication has no meaning if it is not calculated for results.

The function of communication is realized through speech acts. The process of breaking down the communication process into separate speech acts is conditional in nature. Communication functions can only be distinguished for research purposes, since communication usually implies the exchange of addressee and addresser roles and the "intersection and overlap" of functions. After all, communication is continuous interaction in the process of mutual relations.

Researchers distinguish the following functions of messages and communicative acts:

- Warning
- Advice
- Information
- Persuasion
- Expression of opinion
- Entertainment

Here we can add other functions: emotional, poetic, referential. In separate acts of communication, we find informational, imperative, managerial, magical, and ethnic functions. For the analysis of the communication process, it is best to present it in the form of a model. In a model, we can schematically present its constituent elements and functional characteristics. Claude Elwood Shannon's model is widely discussed; he introduced the concept of "language redundancy" into linguistics. Also noteworthy is Marshall McLuhan's method, which considers that the main thing in communication is the communication channel itself. Linguist Roman Jakobson believes that in communication the addresser

transmits a message to the addressee through code:

Context – Message - Speaker – Listener – Channel – Code.

What is meant by context? This is the content of the message and the situation in which the utterance is produced; the channel is the written or oral form of communication; the code is the language in which the utterance is produced.

Jakobson's model is used in linguistics for analyzing both the function of language as a whole and the functioning of its individual units—language and text. Separately, we must distinguish the most important concept for communication—the goal. That for which a person establishes interaction. In the 20th century, the direction of intentionalism emerged, whose followers take into account the speaker's initial intention (plan, subjective meaning) and the listener's interpretation.

M. Bakhtin's ideas had a great influence on the formulation (understanding) of the essence of the communication process. He asserts that the essential characteristic of any utterance is its directionality: there is no speaker without a listener, no addresser without an addressee. And second—any utterance acquires meaning only in context, at a specific time and place. Roland Barthes proposed the hypothesis that a word only has the possibility of expressing meaning—it acquires meaning only in a specific text. This hypothesis undermines the communication model based on the idea of "transmission-reception." Julia Kristeva proposed and expanded the hypothesis about the "citation mosaicism" (intertextuality) of any text. She believes that the receiver of a message becomes an indirect co-author. The intertextual allusions of the receiving subject influence the perception of transmitted information, the interpretation of the message, the reception of the desired effect—that is, the goal of the linguistic phenomenon.

They distinguish the communication process and its constituent acts. Each type of communication, as a necessary component, contains a goal—that is, that toward which communication is directed. A complex of communicative acts united by a common task and situational conditions (environment) is called a communicative event. In the business sphere, this might be a presentation; in politics—a political figure's visit; in education—a lecture, and so forth.

The development of information means produced mass communication, which, in turn, led us to the sphere of management. The process of global transformation of industrial society into information-communication society occurring in the contemporary world is characterized by the penetration of communication into all spheres of social life, the emergence and development of new types of communication structures and processes, which requires a deep understanding of the communicative nature of social reality.

Since communication is the process of transmitting messages and information, the statement is relevant: "He who possesses information also possesses power."

Types of Communication:

Basic Types:	Additional Types
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrapersonal (internal dialogue) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intercultural (communication between those with different cultures; can be interpersonal and inter-group)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpersonal (two or more communicants; can be verbal and non-verbal) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International (at the level of international contacts, including diplomacy)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group (between individual groups or groups, also according to the scheme—communicant and group, for example, a politician's interview) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational (communication in business and production spheres) and • Business communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass (the sender can be one communicant, the receiver—the masses or the electorate during a pre-election campaign). Specificity is determined by communication channels: press, radio, television. • Public (interpersonal, for example, lecturer, public figure—audience) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political (reflects the sphere of political activity; carried out both between individuals and between governing and governed circles)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual (can be interpersonal, group; can have a mass character. Specificity is determined by communication channels based on computer-communication technologies) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Everyday (primarily interpersonal, contains age and gender components)

For a communicative act, one must select the communication strategy, tactics, and intention that determine an individual's communicative action. Consequently, at the center of researching communication problems stands the individual—the "communicative personality," which implies the individual's communicative competence. The constituent elements of communicative competence are: individual communication strategy and tactics, and cognitive, semiotic, and motivational advantages formed in the communication process.

Conclusion: The universal means of communication is articulated sound language, which is characteristic only of humans. At the same time, language is common to a society speaking the same language. Despite the fact that societies differ in the words they use and their grammatical or syntactic systems, nevertheless, all languages serve the same purpose:

1. A person uses language to define, designate, characterize, and delimit something;
2. A person uses language for evaluation. Through the use of language, one expresses positive or negative attitudes;

3. A person uses language to discuss and consider objects and phenomena that exist beyond their immediate experience. Language gives us the means to hypothetically reason about and discuss past and future events, about people and objects that are not beside us at that moment.

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